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List of abbreviations

ISW	In Silico World
WP	Work Package
HPC	High Performance Computing
MEE	Model Execution Environment
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
API	Application Programming Interface
DMT	Deep Modelling Track
DAT	Deep Accreditation Track
ATMP	Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products
FAME	Fractional flow reserve versus Angiography for Multivessel Evaluation trial
FEM	Finite Element Method
MPI	Message Passing Interface
OTLP	OpenTelemetry Protocol

1. Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to report on strategies adopted in the ISW project to ensure operational efficiency and smooth processing of large-scale workflows with the use of research models developed in the project, and through the Model Execution Environment (MEE) (1), identifying and resolving performance bottlenecks which arise when computations are submitted to the available High Performance Computing resources.

The cornerstone of the developed solution is rich monitoring of the scientific applications and the HPC computing infrastructure based on the modern observability principles. *Observability* adopts a holistic approach, using a suite of methodologies, strategies, and tools designed to gather and analyze detailed telemetry data. The primary goal of observability is to uncover unrecognized issues and investigate the “unknown unknowns” that plague the underlying computer systems and applications (2). Existing observability technologies emerged in the context of cloud-native systems and commercial applications, hence their adoption to scientific applications in HPC environments is not straightforward. Key challenges include collection of application-level metrics, instrumentation of scientific applications to collect rich telemetry data, and tracing of distributed call chains in the HPC execution ecosystem.

The solution described in this document is based on open-source standard and tools: the OpenTelemetry (3) observability framework, the OpenSearch (4) data search and analysis engine, Grafana (5), and JupyterHub (6) providing a notebook-based environment for advanced analysis of the collected telemetry data.

The remainder of this document is structured as follows. Section 2 briefly describes the scientific applications monitored using the proposed system. Section 3 introduces the architecture and implementation details of the monitoring system. Section 4 presents examples of performance monitoring and analytical capabilities of developed system. Section 5 highlights optimization conducted based on the data analytics capabilities of the monitoring system. Section 6 concludes work.

2. Executing computational models on HPC – outline

The monitoring system developed in ISW project was design to work in HPC environment. All computations monitored during development of system used Model Execution Environment, Slurm (7) and was run on Ares supercomputer held in Academic Computer Center (ACC) Cyfronet (8). The system was evaluated by two computation models: BoneStrength and AngioSupport.

2.1 BoneStrength

The BoneStrength model follows approach called Digital Twin (9). It represents in-silico models of real life objects, in this case hip bone. Two approaches to BoneStrength were developed: the Standard version and the Markov version, both wrapped into a workflow available for usage on the Model Execution Environment. The standard version is concentrated on running multiple simulation for single patient with various parameters. The Markov version was designed to facilitate the simulation of set of generated fall conditions, in form of campaign for the cohort of patients.

A single simulation of one fall condition, supported by Intel MPI, requires the following resources: 4 CPUs, 8 GB of memory, and 5 GB of disk space for ANSYS (10) software. With this resource allocation, a single simulation typically takes between 10 and 20 minutes to complete.

The most computationally expensive are BoneStrength in-silico trials, which are a practical use case to estimate the risk of bone fracture within a set of patients in form of campaign simulation. A single campaign simulates thousands of falls under varying conditions. This type of experiment utilizes a structured workflow that submits an array job to the HPC cluster, with the job size determined by the number of cases to be processed in the campaign.

2.2 AngioSupport

AngioSupport model can be used both as a clinical decision support system and In Silico Trial tool for myocardial infarction. Currently, the complete 1D model has been adapted which is running on default Slurm (7) allocation since it uses single core and not require significant amount of memory.

The AngioSupport model is executed through two primary methods: as an array of simulations for a cohort of different patients (one simulation per patient) and as a batch of multiple simulations for a single patient. In the first approach, each patient is assigned an individual Slurm (7) job, allowing all computations to occur in parallel. In the second approach, up to 300 worker nodes are instantiated to distribute the simulation tasks. Each worker is pre-assigned a subset of simulations to process, ensuring efficient parallel execution across the allocated resources. The duration of individual simulations varied during the development of the monitoring system, starting at approximately 20 minutes and eventually decreasing to around 15 minutes.

2.3 Deployment

Both described models are well-suited for evaluating the solution. While each MPI-based simulation requires substantial computational resources, the large cohort size further necessitates parallel execution as Slurm array jobs. Additionally, the Model Execution Environment, which features the monitoring platform, is ideally suited for various models, enabling the execution of multi-step pipelines for multiple patients.

Within project every model were executed as pipeline in Model Execution Environment. To execute code via MEE user must provide bash script which executes calculations. Monitoring can be added to any script by injecting prepared code [Code 1]

```
wget -q https://raw.githubusercontent.com/SanoScience/observability/develop/monitoring.sh https://raw.githubusercontent.com/SanoScience/observability/develop/monitoring-env.yml
source monitoring.sh
CASE_NUMBER="param_or_empty {{ case_number }}" ; PIPELINE_IDENTIFIER="param_or_empty {{ pipeline_identifier }}" ; PIPELINE_NAME="param_or_empty {{ pipeline_name }}" ;
STEP_NAME="param_or_empty {{ step_name }}"

setup_env monitoring-env.yml
run_monitoring "--case-number $CASE_NUMBER --pipeline-identifier $PIPELINE_IDENTIFIER --pipeline-name $PIPELINE_NAME --step-name $STEP_NAME" &
```

Code 1: Code insertion responsible for downloading and running monitoring

At its core, the monitoring system operates independently of the application. It is designed to be added to any application working on Slurm HPC environment. During the monitoring of various simulations for selected computational models, it was observed that in some cases, it is necessary to allow for its adaptation to specific scientific applications.

One of AngioSupport methods is designed to run multiple small simulations for a single patient. These simulations are distributed among up to 300 workers to optimize resource utilization, with each worker running as an individual Slurm job. To monitor resource usage for each simulation, we instrumented the AngioSupport application. Model implementation was updated to extract and expose information about running simulations to an external monitoring system. This instrumentation allows the model to send real-time information about the ongoing simulations to the monitoring system during computation. Communication between the instrumented application and the monitoring system occurs via a shared file system.

3. Monitoring infrastructure

This section describes the process of developing a monitoring system aimed at improving the performance of computational models mentioned in section above. It presents the architecture of the monitoring system and details the tools utilized in its implementation. The section also illustrates how the designed monitoring system interacts with the HPC architecture to collect comprehensive telemetry data.

While working with HPC infrastructures and computational models running on these machines, a lack of tools enabling effective monitoring of large-scale computations' performance was observed. To address problem part of ISW project started working on creating solution to this problem. While designing the architecture [Figure 1], we focused on analysing open-source tools to leverage existing solutions in creating a complex monitoring system intended for use in HPC environments. To develop universal solution for working in HPC environment monitoring system strictly cooperate with Slurm workload manager. The system was designed to collect and store metrics and traces from the runtime of scientific applications.

Figure 1: Developed monitoring system architecture

Monitoring system was designed as external service and operates on a virtual machine hosted on a physical machine owned by Sano, located in Kraków, and funded by ISW resources. The idea behind this was to prepare working environment to collect, store and provide telemetry data, ready to be used anytime by scientists running calculations on HPC machines. The services running on this virtual machine are located in the lower part of the architecture [Figure 1] and operate as collaborating Docker containers. These include OpenTelemetry Collector (11), Data Prepper (12), OpenSearch, Jaeger, Grafana, OpenSearch Dashboards, and APM Data Analyzer. The containers communicate with each other through assigned ports on the virtual machine, and the data flow is illustrated in Figure 1.

On the HPC machine side, the monitoring system operates by using the `monitoring.sh` script. When the pipeline containing Code 1 is executed on the HPC machine, a process is triggered that retrieves this script from the Sano GitHub repository (13) and initiates the environment installation. To ensure that all monitoring programs for individual Slurm jobs function consistently, a single Conda (14) environment is installed in the user's SCRATCH folder. This environment includes all necessary dependencies for monitoring the application and is subsequently activated. The environment installation is performed only once to avoid duplication of work across multiple running jobs, allowing them to use the already prepared environment. The next step is to execute the monitoring script in the available environment, which is responsible for creating and sending telemetry data to the OpenTelemetry Collector.

First selected open-source solution was OpenTelemetry framework. It delivers important mechanisms and associated software for, among others, manual and automatic instrumentation, context propagation, and a vendor-neutral OpenTelemetry collector for data distribution. The OpenTelemetry framework was used for creating, processing, and distributing metrics and traces.

The services OpenTelemetry Collector, Data Prepper, OpenSearch operate by processing data in compliance with OpenTelemetry standards. The monitoring system operates with two data streams: one responsible for metrics and the other for traces.

3.1 Metrics

The first and primary data stream is dedicated to metrics, which enable users to gather comprehensive information about resource consumption during the calculations. For that stream we use several components such as OpenTelemetry-collector, Data Prepper, OpenSearch (database) and multiple visualisation tools (Grafana, OpenSearch dashboard and APM data analyser)

All metric data are generated by script running in background of scientific calculations on HPC machine. Script: *scrap-metrics.py* from GitHub repository (13) is responsible for creating metrics by reading data about resource consumption by every Slurm job over time. To collect metrics from a HPC machine, the *cgroups* (15) Linux kernel feature was used. Control Groups (*cgroups*) manage groups of processes running in the Linux kernel. It allows monitoring resource utilization of processes running in the same group. The key feature of *cgroups* in the case of monitoring jobs is the organization of processes into a hierarchical structure. Data about *cgroups* in which the monitored job is running provide the information needed for the observability architecture to extract metric data. The collected metrics include data on the job's memory usage, CPU usage, and the number of open and active files.

The *scrap-metrics.py* script includes numerous functions for reading data on HPC resource usage during computations. It leverages the mechanism provided by the OpenTelemetry framework, specifically the MeterProvider (16), which facilitates the creation of meter instances responsible for individual data points [Code 2]. To obtain a continuous dataset of metrics throughout the entire computation runtime, all meter instances cyclically transmit telemetry data in the background, from the start of the computation until its completion.

```
def observable_gauge_usage_func(options: CallbackOptions) -> Iterable[Observation]:
    yield Observation(read_single_memory_stat('memory.usage_in_bytes'), metric_labels)

gauge_usage = meter.create_observable_gauge("slurm_job_memory_usage", [observable_gauge_usage_func])

def observable_gauge_cpu_percentage_func(options: CallbackOptions) -> Iterable[Observation]:
    cpu_percentage_usage = read_cpu_percentage_usage()
    yield Observation(cpu_percentage_usage, metric_labels)

gauge_usage_cpu_percentage = meter.create_observable_gauge("slurm_job_cpu_percentage_usage", [observable_gauge_cpu_percentage_func])
```

Code 2: Code fragment responsible for meter creation.

Metrics and traces collected during the execution of scientific computations require filtering, parsing, and distribution to the appropriate services. For this purpose, the architecture [Figure 1] includes the OpenTelemetry Collector and Data Prepper components.

In the monitoring system architecture [Figure 1], the collector occupies a central position, as all telemetry data collected during the execution of scientific applications flows through it. The collector consists of a layer that receives telemetry data from its sources, a processing layer, and an export layer that sends the data to designated recipients. An important feature of the collector is its independence from the data source. It can collect data from various sources (OTLP (17), Jaeger,

Prometheus) and pass it to the processing phase, where the data undergoes filtering and distribution processes. At this stage, the data is converted to the OpenTelemetry Protocol (OTLP). Data Prepper is an OpenSearch tool responsible for gathering and processing incoming metric data. This component batches data and send it in proper form to OpenSearch Database.

For gathering metric data OpenSearch was used. OpenSearch is a distributed search and analytics engine based on the document concept. In OpenSearch, documents are units of information storage and can consist of either textual or structured data. In the monitoring system, the OpenSearch service is maintained in a separate Docker container and is responsible for storing metric data. Metrics can be written to and read from the service through the exposed API [Figure 2].

```
{
  "size": 10000,
  "query": {
    "bool": {
      "must": [
        {"term": {"metric.attributes.user": "name"}},
        {"term": {"name": "slurm_job_memory_total_rss"}},
        {"range": {"time": {"gte": "2024-03-21T10:17:47.908Z", "lte":
          ↪ "2024-03-21T10:27:47.908Z"}}}
      ]
    }
  },
  "aggs": { "sampled_data": { "date_histogram": { "field": "time",
    ↪ "min_doc_count": 0, "order": {"_key": "asc"} } } },
  "sort": [
    {"time": {"order": "asc"}}
  ]
}
```

Figure 2: Example of usage OpenSearch API for getting metric data.

In monitoring system open-source solutions, such as the Grafana or OpenSearch dashboards are used for metric visualisation. Such tools provide the user with an easily accessible set of dashboards with predefined charts. One advantage of dashboards is that they can be used in a semi-online fashion, allowing to monitor jobs while they are running.

The use of Grafana enabled the creation of ready-to-use dashboards [Figure 3] consisting of charts that display resource usage, such as memory and CPU. During the development of the monitoring system, several Grafana dashboards were created to enable the monitoring of both currently consumed resources by ongoing computations and historical data. These dashboards provide an overview of key metrics, such as RSS memory usage, cache memory usage, and CPU core utilization. Additionally, a dedicated dashboard was developed to monitor the AngioSupport application after its instrumentation, utilizing information on the simulation numbers executed on the workers. To allow users to explore the collected metrics independently, the prepared dashboards are customizable.

Figure 3: Grafana dashboard showing actual metric data about resource utilization of BoneStrength simulation.

OpenSearch dashboards [Figure 4] provide a useful feature for displaying entire OpenSearch documents containing metric data. In the created monitoring system, this is not a tool for visualizing metric summaries. Instead, it is used for in-depth analysis of individual metrics and the debugging process. Thanks to the ability to analyse collected metrics in such detail, summaries have been prepared in tools like Grafana and the APM data analyser, which present resource usage throughout the entire execution of scientific computations

Figure 4: OpenSearch dashboard usage providing detailed information about resource utilization

During the execution of real-world scientific computations for the BoneStrength and AngioSupport models, it became apparent that a more flexible environment is required for the comprehensive analysis of resource consumption across various simulations. The existing tools, such as Grafana, do not provide users with the ability to create fully customized data reports. To address this limitation, we developed the APM Data Analyzer module. This module operates on a JupyterHub server, providing users with a notebook preconfigured with functionalities for retrieving data from OpenSearch, along with essential methods for data processing and visualization.

The APM Data Analyzer allows users to create custom data aggregations [Figure 5] and more advanced visualizations. Each user is provided with a pre-configured notebook that demonstrates the tool’s capabilities, particularly for monitoring resource utilization.

Figure 5: APM data analyser usage example – rss memory usage metric aggregation.

The APM Data Analyzer provided the opportunity to create a variety of targeted visualizations based on data collected from the BoneStrength and AngioSupport models. Several specific charts were developed, including:

- memory usage of all jobs over time
- timeline of executing jobs
- per-job and per-simulation charts

The introduction of the APM Data Analyzer service provides researchers with an environment to create custom telemetry data summaries. Despite offering predefined functionalities to assist in generating basic data summaries, this service is built on open, modifiable Jupyter notebooks, enabling users to retrieve and filter data in any desired manner.

3.2 Traces

The second data stream in the monitoring system are traces. Traces are important in an observability architecture, as they are responsible for gathering information about data flow in distributed systems. Trace analysis can provide information about the time spans in which a specific job was executed and its execution context.

The initial use of tracing focused on generating information about the performance of scientific computations at the levels of the Model Execution Environment (MEE), Rimrock (18), and the HPC machine. During experiments, it was quickly observed that insights based on the application's

behaviour itself were more valuable. To address this, tracing was integrated into AngioSupport through its instrumentation. Using the OpenTelemetry framework, traces were created to describe the internal operations of workers running multiple simulations.

Figure 6: Trace example from running AngioSupport model after instrumentation.

Code added to the AngioSupport application generates traces for each worker (where a worker corresponds to a Slurm job), with spans representing the execution times of individual simulations. These traces were sent to the OpenTelemetry Collector and propagated to the Jaeger service, responsible for storing and visualizing them. The visualization [Figure 6] of traces enabled convenient and precise analysis of the time required to complete individual simulations and allowed the detection of failed simulations along with their frequency per worker.

3.3 Communication

Communication with the developed monitoring system can be divided into two channels: one for transmitting telemetry data to the service for storage and another for retrieving data from the service to generate summaries and visualizations. Both channels rely on communication via exposed HTTP endpoints.

The first channel operates via an endpoint exposed by the OpenTelemetry Collector, which listens on a designated port. The address of this endpoint is specified in the monitoring.sh script, which is retrieved and executed through code insertion [Code 1]. The monitoring script cyclically sends telemetry data to the specified port in the format defined by OpenTelemetry.

The second channel relies on communication with the OpenSearch database, which exposes its own REST API, enabling the retrieval of raw, filtered, or aggregated metric data. This API is utilized by all services that visualize metrics, including Grafana, OpenSearch Dashboards, and the APM Data Analyzer. The communication is conducted through HTTP queries. Both Grafana and OpenSearch Dashboards come with dedicated tools that facilitate interaction with the OpenSearch engine. For the APM Data Analyzer, we developed a script responsible for retrieving data from the database and generating ready-to-use DataFrames. This script is preloaded for every service user, providing immediate access to telemetry data.

4. Evaluation

After deployment of monitoring system on internal machine and creating http endpoints for communication, system was tested with both BoneStrength and AngioSupport model. Both models presented are well-suited for evaluating this solution. MPI-based simulations (BoneStrength) require extensive computational resources, while the large cohort size demands that multiple computations be executed in parallel as Slurm array jobs. Throughout the experiment, we monitored the progress of array tasks in real time, enabling the detection of anomalies and identification of simulation cases with significant deviations. Additionally, we gathered all essential job metrics to facilitate a comprehensive analysis of resource consumption.

The results of most important metrics were prepared as plots via APM data analyser module. They include total residential memory [Figure 7] which is a critical resource, as its exhaustion would crash the computations.

Figure 7: Charts showing BoneStrength rss summarize usage (left) and maximum usage per job (right).

The distribution shown in Figure 7 indicates that maximum memory usage by jobs is relatively consistent, ranging from 7.1 to 8.4 GB. This consistency allows us to choose an optimal job size to maximize HPC node utilization while avoiding overallocation, which could otherwise lead to abnormal termination of computations. With usage of APM data analyser list of useful charts were created. We monitored memory, CPU and file usage among all BoneStrength and AngioSupport calculations.

While working with the models, a need was identified for visualizing detailed metric data segmented by Slurm job and simulation (AngioSupport). To address this, functions were developed to generate grid-based plots [Figure 8], enabling the visualization of selected, filtered data for more targeted analysis.

Figure 8: Grid chart presenting shortest BoneStrength simulations

The functions prepared to generate visualizations per Slurm job enables the analysis of shortest BoneStrength simulations [Figure 8]. Receiving such detailed data on the simulation performance allowed for the detection of single Slurm job which lasted only a couple of seconds. After analysing file input assigned for this simulation error sample was found.

Figure 9: CPU usage: total usage during execution (left) and distribution of maximum usage by jobs (right). All jobs are allocated 4 cpu cores and clearly they achieve this utilization. The overall usage is quite variable with large periodic peaks.

Metrics were also utilized to generate the histogram shown in Figure 9, illustrating the relationship between the number of jobs and their CPU usage. This visualization enables the analysis of

computational demand not only for individual patients but for the entire cohort. The chart reveals that most jobs utilize the maximum allocated resource of 4 CPU cores, a limit imposed by SLURM through the cgroups mechanism. This observation suggests that increasing the resource allocation could potentially enhance efficiency.

AngioSupport pipelines run with monitoring had up to 5000 simulations distributed to 300 workers (Slurm jobs). It contains over 1000 simulations with computational errors which occurrences were accepted by scientists. Monitoring system helps visualise distribution of jobs duration [Figure 10]. Analysis of job distribution over time for AngioSupport revealed substantial variability in job duration.

Figure 10: AngioSupport jobs length distribution (left) and timeline showing

By incorporating enriched metric data, including simulation IDs, it became evident that this issue stemmed from a static allocation of simulations across jobs. At this stage, simulation data had been partitioned into equal subsets and distributed among workers. The issue emerged because simulations prone to errors completed within seconds before producing an error, resulting in an uneven workload. Consequently, workers assigned multiple error simulations completed their tasks much faster than those processing only error-free simulations.

5. Performance optimization examples

During the evaluation of the monitoring system using the BoneStrength and AngioSupport models, numerous model executions were analysed. The study revealed previously undetected errors in the BoneStrength simulations. The most significant achievement of the monitoring system was identifying opportunities to optimize the distribution of simulations among workers in the AngioSupport model.

To address the issue of uneven resource usage in the AngioSupport model, a new solution was implemented. The Dask (19) library was used to create a cluster capable of distributing simulations across workers. By employing load balancing, the variability in worker execution times was significantly reduced [Figure 11]. Consequently, the total runtime of the calculation pipeline

decreased from approximately 4 hours to 3.5 hours [Figure 11]. This load balancing approach not only reduced computation time but also improved the utilization of allocated resources.

Figure 11: AngioSupport jobs length distribution (left) and timeline showing

An additional improvement in using Dask proved to be its ability to accumulate data generated by simulations in real-time. Previously, the outputs from all simulations were saved as files, and an additional pipeline in the Model Execution Environment (MEE) was executed to aggregate these files and prepare a summary of the simulation set. With the use of Dask, all computations are executed through a single pipeline, producing a final aggregated result ready for use.

6. Conclusions and future work

We have presented monitoring system for end-to-end observability of scientific applications in HPC systems. We have identified the main challenges for such a system, such as instrumentation and propagation of the observability context and collection of application-level metrics. To address insufficient capabilities of existing data analysis and visualization tools, we have proposed a data analysis environment based on Jupyter notebooks and DataFrames. The solution was evaluated using two medical scientific pipelines running on a HPC cluster – BoneStrength and AngioSupport. Data analysis and visualization capabilities of the created monitoring framework were presented. A case study was shown in which our monitoring solution helped improve application performance, reducing the makespan of a 5000-simulation campaign by about 12%.

Future work involves, among others, improvement of the capabilities of the data analysis and visualization API and the Jupyter environment, collection of additional telemetry data, and performance analysis of further scientific applications.

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